

STUDY ON PREDICTION OF PENETRATION ENERGY FOR CA/EP COMPOSITE LAMINATES SUBJECTED TO HIGH-VELOCITY IMPACT USING QUASI-STATIC PERFORATION EQUATION AND KINETIC ENERGY MODEL

H. Cho¹, S. Lee¹, I. Kim^{1*}, and K. Woo²

¹ Dept. of Aerospace Eng., Chungnam National University, Daejeon, Korea

² School of Civil Eng., Chungbuk National University, Cheongju, Korea

*Corresponding author (igkim@cnu.ac.kr)

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1 Introduction

Composite materials are widely used in many fields such as aircraft, defense industry etc. because of its high specific strength, specific stiffness compared with metallic materials. However, composites occur brittle fracture easily different from ductile metals and have various damage modes. It is important to investigate impact behavior for composite materials especially used in aircraft structures because of their decline mechanical characteristic subjected to external impact[1]. The quasi-static perforation behavior of composite materials represents the energy absorbing capacity of the structure under transverse loading without dynamic and high strain effect[2]. Thus, actually absorbed energy obtained through quasi-static perforation equation differs from the energy that absorbed during ballistic impact. The models for kinetic energy of specimen are derived based on the previous other researcher's results and examined. Morye et al.[3] classified three major components for composite as 1) tensile failure of the composite 2) elastic deformation of the composite 3) the kinetic energy of the moving portion of the composite. In this paper, we classify absorbed energy into a composite laminates as static term and dynamic term. The static term[2,4,5] are obtained by quasi-static perforation equation and dynamic term obtained by using the modified kinetic energy model based on Morye's work. Finally, we examined and compared absorption energy using theoretical model with high-velocity impact test[6]. The high-velocity impact test is conducted by powder gun under the different test conditions(i.e. bullet diameters = 7.79mm, 5.59mm, initial velocity, $V_i = 600\text{m/s}$, 800m/s). The amount of penetration

energy varies by specimen thickness, mass of projectile and usually tends to increase for the thicker composite specimen. After ballistic impact test, we examine damage area of specimens by using C-Scan[7]. The absorbed energy in specimens during penetration are calculated by using the difference between initial velocity and residual velocity of projectile, and compared with the results predicted by kinetic energy model.

2 Theoretical model

2.1 Absorbed Energy (E_{abs}) based on Projectile

The absorbed energy of impacted specimens are calculated by using the difference between initial and residual velocity of projectile as shown Eqn.(1) in general.

$$E_{abs} = \frac{1}{2}m_p(V_i^2 - V_r^2) \quad (1)$$

However, the loss of projectile should be considered when the projectile is not rigid body but deformable body in such this study. The loss of projectile mass can be observed through the high speed camera image before and after penetration as shown in Fig.1. The absorbed energy is defined such as Eqn.(2).

$$E_{abs} = \frac{1}{2}(m_i V_i^2 - m_r V_r^2) - \frac{1}{2}m_e V_e^2, \quad (m_e = m_i - m_r) \quad (2)$$

Where m_i , m_r , m_e are initial mass, residual mass, and mass loss of projectile, respectively and V_e is the velocity for lost mass of projectile. The kinetic energy for lost mass of projectile is Eqn.(3).

$$E_e = \frac{1}{2} m_e V_e^2 \quad (3)$$

It is impossible to calculate the velocity for the lost mass of projectile in macroscopically and their kinetic energy are calculated under 5 different assumed velocities of lost mass such as 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, 100% of residual velocity. The 100% velocity means rigid projectile and the 0% velocity means the kinetic energy for lost mass is absorbed completely by composite laminates.

2.2 Absorbed Energy (E_{abs}) based on Composite Lamintes

In this paper, we conducted modeling for predicting absorbed energy in composite laminates subjected high-velocity impact. We classify absorbed energy in composite laminates as static term (E_{SE}) and dynamic term (E_{KE}). The total absorption energy in composite laminates (E_{abs}) is given by

$$E_{abs} = E_{SE} + E_{KE} \quad (4)$$

The dynamic term is divided into kinetic energy of deformed specimen (E_{cone}) and kinetic energy of particulates ($E_{particle}$) separated from specimen. The models for kinetic energy of deformed specimen are derived based on the previous other researcher's results[3] and the model for the kinetic energy of particulates was proposed based on the probabilistic approach.

2.2.1 Quasi-static equation (E_{SE})

Wen and Jone[4] defined the absorbed energy of composite laminates as sum of the localized absorption energy (E_l) and global deformation energy of composite (E_g).

$$E_{abs} = E_l + E_g \quad (5)$$

where E_f is absorption energy until composite laminates is perforated.

In this paper, the formula of perforation energy on hemispherical indenter is given by

$$E_f = \sigma_u d^3 \left(\frac{\pi \epsilon_f}{8} + A \left(\frac{D}{d} \right)^{\beta_1} \left(\frac{T}{d} \right)^{\beta_2} \right) \quad (6)$$

where σ_u is failure stress of composite laminates, ϵ_f is fracture strain by tension, d is diameter of indenter, T is thickness of composite laminates, D mean radius of constraint and A, β_1, β_2 are experimental constants.

2.2.2 Modified kinetic energy of the cone formed on the back face of the composite upon ballistic impact (E_{cone})

According to paper of Morye et al.[4], kinetic energy of the moving cone is given by

$$E_{cone} = \frac{1}{2} m_c V_c^2 \quad (7)$$

where m_c is mass of moving cone, V_c is velocity of moving cone. Mass of moving cone is given by

$$m_c = \pi R_c^2 T \rho \quad (8)$$

V_c is assumed that V_c is equal residual velocity of impactor. Thus, kinetic energy of the moving cone is given by

$$E_{cone} = \frac{1}{2} \pi R_c^2 T \rho V_c^2 \quad (9)$$

In this paper, we modified the kinetic energy of moving cone based on Morye's model. Thus, we regard velocity of cone as function of radius of cone formed on the back face of the composite laminates rather than constant velocity. We assume that the cone formed on the back face of the composite laminates is equal to the measured radius of damage area by using C-scan.

(a) case1 ($0 < R_c < R$)

First case, we defined integral interval from center of cone to radius of cone formed on the back face of the composite laminates. The velocity function on radius of cone is given by

$$V_c = -\frac{V_r}{R} r + V_r \quad (10)$$

where V_r is residual velocity of impactor, R is radius of damage area and r is integral variable.

Using the equation (9), we defined the kinetic energy of moving cone in the form of integral

$$E_{cone} = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^R \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{2} r t \rho V_c^2(r) dr d\theta \quad (11)$$

(b) Case2 ($R_i < R_c < R$)

Second case, we defined integral interval from radius of impactor to radius of cone formed on the back face of the composite laminates. Thus kinetic energy of moving cone (E_{cone}) is given by

$$E_{cone1} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{R_i}^R \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{2} r t \rho V_c^2(r) dr d\theta \quad (12)$$

where R_i is radius of impactor.

The second term, we should consider kinetic energy of rest of cone part that has same velocity of projectile.

$$E_{cone2} = \frac{1}{2} \pi R_i t \rho V_r^2 \quad (13)$$

Thus, the kinetic energy for the deformed moving cone is given by

$$E_{cone} = E_{cone1} + E_{cone2} \quad (14)$$

2.3 Kinetic energy of the particulates separated from composite laminates due to ballistic impact($E_{particle}$)

The model for the kinetic energy of particulates was proposed based on the probabilistic approach. Based on the high-speed camera images, the velocities of the particulates separated from specimen are assumed to be normal distribution between initial and residual velocity of projectile and kinetic energy are calculated.

3 Experimental Procedures

3.1 Materials

Used specimen in the this paper used carbon/epoxy unidirectional prepreg(USN 150B, SK chemical). The size of specimen is 87.5X87.5mm and 150X150mm. The stacking sequence is [45/0/-45/90]_{ns} and thickness provided three different thickness of 4.66mm, 6.9mm and 9.29mm. In case of 6.9mm used specimen of 150X150mm and the rest used specimen of 87.5X87.5mm. Material property of prepreg is shown in Table 1.

3.2 High-velocity Impact Test

High-velocity impact test equipment consists of Gun, Specimen, Jig, High speed camera and DAQ ,and Infrared ray photo sensor, Magnetic sensor which are measure the velocity of projectile. High-velocity impact equipment set-up is shown Fig.2. The specimens used in test are fixed by jig that exposed size is 100X100mm, 65X65mm, respectively.

During high-velocity impact test, initial velocity of projectile measured by two magnetic sensor three infrared ray sensors and residual velocity of projectile is measured two magnetic sensor and high-speed camera.

3.2 High speed camera

During high-velocity impact test, we used high speed camera for identifying shape change and movement of projectile. we calculated mass changes of projectile and projectile’s velocity before and after impact by using high-speed camera images.

Table 1. Material property of Ca/Ep prepreg (USN 150B, SK chemicals)

	Symbol	Unit	Value
Young’s modulus along the fiber direction	E_{11}	GPa	181.0
Young’s modulus along the transverse direction	E_{22}	GPa	8.2
Axial shear modulus	G_{12}	GPa	4.6
Axial poisson’s ratio	ν_{12}		0.28
Thickness	h	mm	0.140

4. Results and discussion

4.1 High-velocity Impact Test

Table 2 and 3 show results of high-velocity impact test. We calculated absorbed energy by using projectile's mass and velocities before and after impact. In the case of armor piercing shell bullet, magnetic sensor didn't work and so we measured residual velocity by using high speed camera.

4.2 C-scan images

Fig.3 and 4 present C-scan images after high-velocity impact test. We conducted C-scan with coin of 18mm diameter to check damage area of composite laminates subjected to high-velocity impact.

Table 4 shows maximum diameter of damage area by using C-scan images. In the case of steel core ammunition, maximum diameter of 9.29mm specimen less than 6.9mm specimen and in the case of armor piercing shell ammunition two specimens have similar value. It attribute jig used in the test. The jigs used in high-velocity impact test have exposed area 100x100mm and 65x65mm, respectively. But 6.9mm thickness specimen used 100x100mm jig and 9.29mm thickness specimen used 65x65mm jig.

4.3 Correlation with experimental data and model

Table 5, 6, 7 and 8 present predicted values by using absorbed energy model mentioned earlier. In steel core ammunition and case1 of armor piercing shell case, the dominant energy absorbing mechanism was found to be the static term and in case 2 of armor piercing shell, the dominant energy absorbing mechanism was found to be the dynamic term.

Fig.5 and 6 is graph that is comparison of absorbed energy by using theoretical model and absorbed energy obtained at high-velocity impact test. Case1 is less than case2. But in armor piercing shell case, difference between theoretical model and high-velocity impact test is very large. In the case of steel core ammunition in 9.29mm thick specimen,

the difference between model and measured value are greater than that of other specimens. It is considered to occur due to the size of the jig. The damage area of 9.29mm specimen is less than the area damage area of 6.9mm specimen or similar to the area damage area of 6.9mm specimen. If jig is enough large, damage area of 9.29mm specimen is be predicted to increase and it lead to increase absorbed energy into composite laminates. Through experimental results and the model result we found error of steel core ammunition is less than that of armor piercing shell. In steel core ammunition and case1 of armor piercing shell case, the dominant energy absorbing mechanism was found to be the static term and in case 2 of armor piercing shell, the dominant energy absorbing mechanism was found to be the dynamic term. But in armor piercing shell case, difference between experimental results and the model results are very large. However, after some modification for the kinetic model which included the kinetic energy of particulates, the absorbed energy comparison among the proposed kinetic model, the impact test results and FEA results was shown in Fig.7. The predicted absorbed energy and residual velocity using the proposed empirical formula are agreed well with high-velocity impact test results.

5. Conclusions

The high-velocity impact behaviors for composite laminates can be evaluated by the residual velocity of projectile, the absorbed energy by composite laminates, and their residual strength. In this study, we proposed the empirical formula model for predicting the residual velocity of projectile and the absorbed energy of composite laminates and conducted a comparison with the high-velocity impact test results. The absorbed energy due to high-velocity impact is divided into static energy(E_{static}) and dynamic energy($E_{dynamic}$). The static energy related to elastic energy and failure of fibers and matrix are calculated by using the perforation energy obtained through the quasi-static perforation test. The dynamic energy is divided into kinetic energy of deformed specimen(E_{cone}) and kinetic energy of particulates($E_{particle}$) separated from specimen. The models for kinetic energy of deformed specimen are

derived based on the previous other researcher's results and the model for the kinetic energy of particulates was proposed based on the probabilistic approach.

The main energy transfer/absorption mechanism of impact for the carbon/epoxy laminates in this high velocity regime is thought to be due to not only static perforation energy and kinetic energy of deformed specimen but also the kinetic energy of the particulates of specimen during impact.

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Fig.1. Loss of projectile mass

Fig.2. High-velocity impact test set-up

Fig.3. C-scan images of steel core ammunition
 $(V_i = 600m/s)$

Fig.4. C-scan images of armor piercing shell
 $(V_i = 800m/s)$

Fig.5. Comparison with test and model
 (steel core ammunition)

Fig.6. Comparison with test and model
 (armor piercing shell)

Fig.7. Comparisons with predicted and experimental of absorbed energy

Table 2. Result of high-velocity impact test (steel core ammunition)

	Initial velocity		Residual velocity		Impactor mass(gr)		$E_{abs}(J)$
	Infrared ray	Magnetic	High speed camera	Magnetic	Before Penetration	After penetration	
Specimen thickness							
4.66mm	592.8	592.9	555.8	555.8	3.59	3.59	76.44
6.9mm	611.0	611.0	577.4	557.4	3.59	3.28	160.46
9.29mm	587.2	591.7	508.0	508.0	3.59	3.05	235.17

Table 3. Result of high-velocity impact test
(Armor piercing shell)

Specimen thickness	Initial velocity (m/s)		Residual velocity (m/s)		Impactor mass(gr)		$E_{abs}(J)$
	Infrared ray	Magnetic	High speed camera	Magnetic	Before Penetration	After penetration	
4.66mm	805.5		753.7		10.59	10.58	427.38
6.9mm	805.9		737.8		10.59	8.72	1063.55
9.29mm	802.2		741.3		10.59	8.37	1106.28

Table 4. Diameter of damages

(mm)	Steel core ammunition			Armor piercing shell		
	Specimen Thickness	4.66	6.9	9.29	4.66	6.9
Diameter of damage	41.0	70.21	66.6	40.5	65.2	67.

Table 5. Case1 ($V_i = 600m/s$)for steel core ammunition

Specimen Thickness(mm)	$E_{SE}(J)$	$E_{KE}(J)$	$E_{abs}(J)$
4.66	30.85	4.41	35.26
6.9	57.52	9.56	67.08
9.29	92.15	9.56	102.56

Table 6. Case2 ($V_i = 600m/s$) for steel core ammunition

Specimen Thickness(mm)	$E_{SE}(J)$	$E_{KE1}(J)$	$E_{KE2}(J)$	$E_{abs}(J)$
4.66	30.85	4.20	27.91	62.96
6.9	57.52	9.56	41.56	108.64
9.29	92.15	10.37	46.49	149.01

Table 7. Case1 ($V_i = 800m/s$) for armor piercing shell

Specimen Thickness(mm)	$E_{SE}(J)$	$E_{KE}(J)$	$E_{abs}(J)$
4.66	49.32	7.58	56.90
6.9	91.84	16.10	107.94
9.29	147.13	22.27	169.40

Table 8. Case2 ($V_i = 800m/s$) for armor piercing shell

Specimen Thickness(mm)	$E_{SE}(J)$	$E_{KE1}(J)$	$E_{KE2}(J)$	$E_{abs}(J)$
4.66	49.32	7.47	99.42	156.21
6.9	91.84	15.94	141.06	248.84
9.29	147.13	22.09	191.73	360.95